

**MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PROFESSIONAL
DEVELOPMENT OF A TEACHER**

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The development of teacher skills should be carried out throughout the entire professional activity. Reflection of the achieved quality allows you to identify shortcomings and determine the direction of self-education. This leads to professional creativity and enrichment of experience. The achieved new quality is again subjected to reflection and the ways of self-education are determined. Genuine self-development includes not only a methodological direction, but also the expansion of cultural horizons, ideological and psychological preparation; development of artistry, pedagogical technique.

In the professional and pedagogical activity of a teacher, significant changes are needed that would create conditions for achieving a new quality of education. The development of the teacher's skill, his professional competence is in the hands of the teacher himself and depends on his readiness to engage in self-education. The main conditions for self-education are creativity, experience and reflection. E.V. Piskunova argues that "in modern professional and pedagogical activity, functions are distinguished that are aimed at oneself, at the teacher's own professional growth, that is, the reflexive function and the function of self-education." The teacher acts as the creator of the educational process, constantly analyzing his activities and gaining professional experience on the basis of reflection. This brings the teacher's creativity to a new level, after which reflection follows again and the "piggy bank" of pedagogical experience is replenished. Although it would not be entirely correct to call it a "piggy bank", since the experience gained is constantly used, comprehended and leads to the professional improvement of the teacher. This process does not stop throughout the teacher's pedagogical activity. Choosing a topic for self-education is a difficult and responsible task. This should be preceded by a reflective stage: a thorough and objective analysis of one's own work, the correspondence of the results to the goals and possibilities, taking into account the available resources. It is imperative to analyze the goal set: was it possible to achieve it with a given contingent of students, lack of necessary equipment, etc. Perhaps, initially, the goal did not correspond to the possibilities and was unattainable under certain conditions. If the analysis reveals the problem of insufficient competence of the teacher, which hinders the achievement of a new quality of education, then it becomes decisive in choosing the topic of teacher self-development. Thus,

reflective activity is a prerequisite for the professional growth of a teacher. One of the founders of reflective pedagogy, the British scientist M. Wallace rightly noted: "Practice becomes a source of teacher's professional growth only to the extent that it is an object of structured analysis: non-reflective practice is useless and eventually leads not to development, but to professional stagnation of the teacher".

The concept of "self-education" is much broader than only increasing methodological and subject literacy. M. M. Potashnik proposes to include in the list of areas of self-education, in addition to methodological and didactic, such areas: expanding the cultural horizons, developing the teacher's intellect as a specially organized activity; worldview training; psychological preparation; development of artistry, pedagogical technique, performing skills. Indeed, it is impossible to be a modern teacher without an appropriate cultural and intellectual level. Such a teacher is not interesting to students, he is limited only by knowledge of his subject. It is difficult for him to connect a specific field of knowledge with life, to show its value and significance for the development of the existence of mankind, its history and culture. M. M. Potashnik argues that "a developed intellect, a general culture of a person is the foundation on which any pedagogical technology is built."

As for the worldview training of teachers, in this direction M.M. Potashnik recommends starting with the study of axiology - the theory of values: "Without this fundamental knowledge, no teacher, no matter how well he knows his subject, can provide a good, full-fledged education for children". New requirements for the modern lesson - disclosure for each student of the personal meaning of the material being studied. This cannot be achieved without knowledge of the value bases of the content of the educational material. Incompetence in the field of psychological preparation leads to the constant appearance of "difficult" children, to psychological traumas that make themselves felt all their lives, to the lumpenization of individual students, to broken destinies. And the reason for this is the inability to determine the maximum capabilities of the child, inattention to age and mental characteristics, ignorance of conflictology. The teacher is responsible for the fate of children, therefore, the constant replenishment of psychological knowledge is the professional and moral duty of the teacher.

N.E. Shchurkova also speaks about the development of artistry, pedagogical technique, and performing skills. To underestimate this side of teaching means to abandon an important means of pedagogical influence. "Teachers who are

afraid of acting are doomed to vegetate on the sidelines of pedagogy," M. M. Potashnik warns. The "artistry" of the teacher is a high mastery of performance, virtuosity, which is impossible without training in all of the above areas and requires sincerity and authenticity of experiences from the teacher. So, only the development of the teacher's reflective competence and work in all these areas will lead to qualitative changes in his work.

Self-education of a teacher is not just work on a methodological topic, it is a true self-development and self-improvement, which gives him a sense of personal growth, confidence in his importance and necessity, and awareness of the high mission of the teacher.

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